

Nature and Humanity in the Poetry of Whitman

Dr. Jay Prakash Singh
Garkha, Chapra Bihar

Walt Whitman is widely acknowledged as the poet of romanticism, as well as the concept of the soul's journey and progression, of the never-ending quest for improvement, and the happiness that comes from spiritual development. According to him a writer's primary interest should be the world around them. Consequently, Whitman uses it to bathe us in the flow of an evergrowing foundation, pouring on us constantly the waters of an ever-rising tide, and this cannot be avoided or understood¹(P. 47). This is what makes Whitman so special; he was able to secure a place for himself among the universal voices. The purpose of this article is to investigate the theme of the self in relation to the Nature, which is present on different levels of his poetry. It is a fact that Whitman had true love for common people. His attitude towards common people and their plight was very sensitive, this was the reason he was called the poet of general people but that's not it, he was also majorly interested in Nature. He has composed many poems in which his interest in Nature is reflected in true sense. In this connection he had followed Wordsworthian attitude but he was not so devoted as a worshipper of Nature and her objects, scenes, sounds and rhythmic motion. His approach to Nature was that of a lover of fresh air and fragrant atmosphere. He considered himself as he was not a man of cultivated tastes; therefore his approach to Nature was very naturally obvious. Whitman considers that, Nature does not require any artificial ornamentation, the beauty of nature lies in her wildness only. Whitman thought that poet's approach to nature should be personal and he should take into account the new discoveries of science about nature objects. The poet does not allow the creeds, the religion and philosophy to come in the way of his communion with nature. He wishes his body and soul be fully attended to the heart and the soul of the nature, and also that nature should be allowed to speak to him with all her energy. This communion with nature will vest the poet with power and wisdom. Being a mystic poet his attitude to nature is essentially pantheistic. For him every object in nature is alive and represents the glory of one god. The title of his poem, "Leaves of Grass", is drawn from natural observation of leaves and grasses; these are the symbols of the poet's great fascination for nature. Walt Whitman is quite apt to present the natural instincts of the outer world. He expresses the natural

instincts in a very good direction. He writes:

*“Lo, the unbounded sea,
On its breast a ship starting, spreading allSails, even her
moon sails,
The pennant is flying aloft as she
speeds, so stately below emulous waves press forward, they
surround
the ship with shining curving motionsand foam. (P. no
12)”*²

Whitman’s love of nature is quite glorious as he writes: *As I walked in*

*Alabama my morning walk,I have seen where she – bird, also
the
Mocking bird sat on her nest in the barrier Hatching her brood,
have seen the he – birdalso I have paused to hear him near at the
hand inflating his throat and joyfullysinging (Section
– 11 P. 22)”*.

The first section of “song of myself” strikes the keynote of Whitman’s feeling about nature. He expresses his sympathy for all human beings and animals from birds and trees, leaves and flowers etc. In this context Whitman writes Whitman presents a true picture of real knowledge and wisdom in the context of nature. It should be indicated that Whitman’s study of nature slightly differs from that of Wordsworth. Nature to Wordsworth is not the nature to Whitman. It is a healing balm and a teacher to Wordsworth while Whitman considers that nature was to be drawn upon for the evolution of the humanity and its betterment.

It was known to all, that nature doesn’t isolate a man from people, in fact nature was a contributory force towards the mortal and spiritual uplift of a man. Nature, in an oblique manner helps a man without asking him to be her votary. Wordsworth is enamored of nature where as Whitman has merged his entire self entity in the limitless cosmos. Here we

get the difference between Wordsworth and Whitman, In this context, we may refer to his own statement:

“The effects he produces in his poems are no effect of artists or the arts, but effects of the original eye or arm, or the actual atmosphere, the unconscious teaching of a fine brute but will never feel the artificial teaching of a fine writer or speaker (P. no. 777).”

It is a common conception that Walt Whitman glorifies animal world and advances the plea for a return to the elemental simplicities of life because they're in lie, peace contentment and happiness. Walt Whitman describes the materialistic craze of his contemporaries in a purely Wordsworthian vein. The animals do not spend sleepless and agonized nights and do not shed tears for the atonement of their sins. They are above the common frailties of mankind. They do not indulge in fruitless philosophical discourses and never go crazy with their possessive instincts.

They never suffer from the sense of servility and sycophancy. To Whitman this world of animals is an item of glory and he establishes a relation between himself and the animals. The poet writes :

*“They do not sweat and whine about their condition,
They do not lie awake in the dark and weep for their sins, They do not make sick
discussing their duty to god,
Not one is dissatisfied, not one is demented with the Mania of owning things, not one
kneels to another,
Nor to his kind that lived thousands of years ago (Section – 32 P
no. 60).”*

Nature is an excuse for the mystic experiences of the poet. Whitman runs closely parallel to Blake when the latter can have a glimpse of divinity even in the grain of sand. Whitman does lag far behind. To Wordsworth even the meanest flower was an item of conscience, and to Whitman, nature spreads in time and space bears the mystic stars veil of divinity. Even then Whitman is dallying with the delicate, beautiful aspects of nature; Whitman's love for

nature approximates Keats's when he indulges in details. Here the poet expresses his view in a very comparable manner:

*“Living bulbs, melons with polished rinds
Smooth to the reached hand. Bulbs of life, Lilies, polished
melons, flavored for the Mildest hand that shall reach (P.
no.699).”*

Whitman does not agree with Keats so far as the meanings behind the sensations are concerned. Keats aims at converting beauty into truth and vice versa but Whitman's adventurous journey leads us to real realities. Truth has got a deeper significance, a mystic significance foreign to Keats. These lines are quite remarkable in this context;

*“And I or you pocket less of a dime mayPurchase the pick
of the Earth
And to glance with an eye or show a Bean confounds the
learning of all times(Section-48 P. 86).”*

Whitman's style of versification has its root in the Bible, which may be seen in countless passages.

*“What is man, that thou art mindful of him? And the Son of man,
that thou visited him? For thou has to made him a little lower
thanthe angles, and has crowned him with gloryand honor
(Section 48 P. 88).”*

While the 'political' argument that comradely love can be used to build new democratic societies is more believable in some of Whitman's poem, the tenderness of danger of adhesiveness as he describes it, is more conveyed and more convincing in the 'Calamous' poems. Nature was the source of Whitman's deepest impressions in his early years, and the source of his spiritual realization. Walt Whitman was quite apt to offer an unstinted admiration to a life close to nature and a life free of vulgar materialism. Whitman derives the substance from nature as he deals with life and nature and validity of his views. He indulgently pictures the sensuous beauty of nature when he smells “the white roses sweet

scented and growing” and touches “the leafy lips” or the “polished breasts of melons”. It should be indicated that Whitman’s deep interest in cosmology relates to the process of evolution and his admiration for the wonder and the mysterious forces, that comes out of chaos. This cosmic infinite expanse heightens the poet’s mystic ecstasy and experiences where nature is a symbolic representation of the infinite and it prompts the poet to establish an affinity between man and nature. Walt Whitman expresses this view and writes:

*“For it in the nebula cohered to an orb, The long slow
strata filed to rest it on Vast vegetables gave it
sustenance, Monstrous sauroids transported it in
Their mouths and deposited it with care All forces have
been steadily employed To complete and delight me, Now
on This spot I stand with my robust soul
(Section – 44 P. 81)”*

Whitman’s mystical experiences are incommunicable as that of Shelley’s ‘Skylark’.

*“Teach us spyrte or bird what sweet thoughts Are thyne:
I never heard.
Praise of love and wine hat panted forth flood Of rapture so divine
(To A Skylark P. 245)”*

Walt Whitman with a deep sense of humility bequeaths hemlock to the dearth from where he will grow in the form of grass which has always been after his heart’s desire. The poet learnt the lessons of humility through the mystical experiences. It is a fact that a single blade of grass has set the poet to mysterious thinking with an added sense of spirituality. No item of nature to the poet is insignificant and he easily identifies his self with it.

References

Callow, Philip. From Noon to Starry Night: A Life of Walt Whitman. Chicago : Ivan R. Dec, 1992.

Walt Whitman, Leaves of Grass, A Norton Critical Edition, ed. Sculley Bradley and Harold Boldgett, (New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India PVT., 1986), "The Ship Starting".

Shelly: "To a Skylark", Palgrave's Golden Treasury (Calcutta Oxford University Press)